

DEFIBRATION OF SOLID WOOD WASTE AND POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARDS: THE mTMP PROCESS

OVERVIEW

Fibreboards are widely used in Europe for furniture, packaging, flooring and construction, but their production still relies mainly on virgin wood. As demand increases, there is a growing need to diversify supply to relieve pressure on natural resources and improve industry resilience. Wood waste, could replace a significant share of virgin wood, turning it into a valuable secondary raw material to produce new fibreboards once remaining technical barriers are addressed.

PROCESS

One promising approach to overcome these barriers is the moisture modifying thermo-mechanical pulping (mTMP) process which tackles the main technical limitation of wood waste: its low moisture content.

With only minor adjustments to existing industrial plants, the technology enables the production of fibres for medium- and high-density fibreboard (MDF, HDF) and insulation material from various waste wood streams, including dry solid wood and post-consumer fibreboards. Recycled wood chips are first moistened using a specially designed device, then heated and softened in the digester. Mechanical treatment in the refiner finally transforms the chips into fibres with a size distribution comparable to those obtained from virgin wood.

ACHIEVEMENTS

EcoReFibre Demonstration C: The mTMP process advanced from TRL 5 to TRL 6, producing high-quality fibres for fibreboard production with infeed including up to 25% recycled post-consumer fibreboard or solid wood waste. In addition, it provides valuable data for industrial upscaling.

OPTIMISED TMP REFINER FOR FIBRE EXTRACTION

The mTMP process has been advanced in a first phase optimising the process parameters for a batch-based defibration system (TRL5), producing high-quality fibres from post-consumer fibreboards or solid wood waste. Fibre size and type distribution were comparable to those of virgin wood, demonstrating the potential of the technology for industrial application. Dust levels, an indicator of effective humidification of dry waste wood, were significantly reduced, improving fibre yield and handling.

In the second phase, a continuous process was developed (TRL6), marking progress towards industrial upscaling. Trials with different defibration parameters, including variations in steam pressure, retention time and grinding gap, ensured consistent fibre quality. For now, the trials showed that prioritising uncoated boards for recycling is required to maintain fibre quality. The generated process data, close industry collaboration, and preparatory design work, now underpin the industrial upscaling and integration of the mTMP process.

WOOD FIBRES FROM POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARD AND SOLID WOOD CHIPS

ONGOING R&D

Ongoing R&D activities focus on further optimising the defibration process to ensure high fibre quality across different waste wood sources. This includes developing technologies optimising fibre saturation through enhanced steam penetration into wood chips to maintain fibre properties regardless of their initial moisture content.

In parallel, IHD is studying the chemical properties, such as formaldehyde content and pH, which differ from those of virgin wood fibres. This research will help better understand how these properties affect emissions, bonding performance and identify ways to optimise them for fibreboard production.

NEXT STEPS

The next steps focus on increasing process speed, streamlining production, and scaling up the mTMP technology in close cooperation with the fibreboard industry. This includes focusing on final adjustments and process optimisation to meet industrial fibre quality requirements. Together, these advances will bring the technology closer to industrial adoption and support a more resource-efficient fibreboard sector.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based, carbon storing material, wood is a key driver of Europe's circular bioeconomy. Recycling post-consumer wood waste into insulation products helps extend the lifespan of wood while offering high-quality envelope materials for buildings. Through recycling, carbon is stored and dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

Innovations such as advanced waste-sorting lines, optimised TMP refiners and other smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life wood-based materials to be broken down into fibres and particles suitable for reuse in new panels. Industrial trials have shown that MDF can incorporate up to 25% recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

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